

Impact of COVID-19 on seafarers and their employment decisions under the new normal

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Abstract

The COVID-19 or earlier known as the novel coronavirus is currently affecting the world in many ways. This study aimed to focus on COVID-19, the cruise line industry and how it has been affected, as well as the seafarers' decision on going back to work under the new normal. Further, this study attempted to answer demographic questions such as seafarers' age, gender, cruise line company the seafarers have worked with, years of service in their respective companies and their level of well-being based on their physical, mental, financial, and emotional state. Moreover, this study attempted to know if there is a significant relationship between the seafarers' current physical, mental, financial and emotional states and their decision on going back to work. This research was conducted using quantitative approach and descriptive research design. A total of 50 seafarers, 18 males and 32 females, were chosen as respondents in the survey using simple random sampling. Eventually this study revealed that the seafarers' physical, mental and emotional health are fit, which explains that the seafarers are capable of going back to work. In conclusion, there is a significant relationship between the seafarers' current emotional, physical financial, and mental states and their decision on going back to work. The study also revealed that the seafarers are deemed well-accounted for, which means they are ready to return to work and the work environment is conducive to them.

Keywords: COVID-19; seafarers; new normal; employment decision.

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Introduction

The COVID-19, or earlier known as the novel coronavirus is currently affecting the world in many ways. With only a small amount of vaccine available and even small ways to treat those who were infected, nonpharmaceutical interventions became the main solution to combat the spread of the virus. The major effect of the global economy's fall-down is due to the lockdown in which travelling is restricted and most are advised to stay at home. The last major global loss that occurred was during the World War II. There were approximately 90% of the population affected by the travel bans and restrictions on public gatherings, and this resulted in a large cease in the tourism industry during March 2020. Air travel, cruises, and the accommodation industry were heavily affected (Gössling et al., 2020).

According to the World Health Organization (2020), there was an unknown cause of pneumonia that was discovered in Wuhan, China. Earlier in January 2020, 41 confirmed infected patients with COVID-19 had been put in hospitals in China (Huang et al., 2020). The virus escalated throughout Wuhan, China but leaders of some countries did not give attention to it which contributed to the easy spread of the virus throughout the world (Harris et al., 2020). Wuhan has come to a state when it needed to quarantine people to contain the virus. By the middle of February the number of COVID cases in China stabilized at 80,000.

According to an article by Mercene and Medenilla (2020), about half of the 100,000 Filipino seafarers have lost their jobs. One of the most affected were the major cruise operators, which in effect greatly affected the seafarers, and the cruise ship industry was expected to resume operations by the end of 2020, while canceling schedules until the last quarter of the year due to the pandemic. Travel consultant Manny Geslani explained that there were about 50,000 to 60,000 Filipino seafarers out of 130,000 who were employed and were not able to work due to the huge impact of the pandemic to the cruise ship industry. Geslani stated that there were about 12,000 new batch of seafarers from major cruise lines who would have returned home to the Philippines in April until May of 2020. Ships were expected to arrive with Filipino crews coming from Asia, Australia, Europe, and the United States. Before these ships would have docked at the Manila port, they would have already been given permissions, as well as instructions in observing health and safety protocols, which included identifying returning sailors, who have been isolated in their individual vessels before their appearance, and would, in any case, need to go through the required 14-day home quarantine.

According to Cruise Industry News (2021), after the resumption of cruise ship operations, more than a thousand crew members were already back on board to work to their respected cruise ships, and whether or not they experienced difficulties in getting on board due to the pandemic. Most of them responded that they were contacted a few times before their joining dates while some were asked if they would like to resume working already, as well as further details for those who accepted the offer. Before the crew members reported to their respective assignments in the cruise industry, they were expected to undergo two to three COVID tests. As for their respective country's protocol, they would undergo a test first before they are granted permission to travel. Once they reached their destination, they would undergo a polymerase chain reaction (PCR) test while being quarantined and would have another one when onboard.

Once the contract would be signed by the employee and the cruise line's management, it would then be finalized and would usually take a longer time than usual. Majority of the crew members who were reemployed stated that they were happy that they have been able to return to work as well as thankful to the cruise line for the assistance extended to their application. Although they also noticed that there was an evident change in their situation now, they also observed that there were fewer applicants and that they have to observe social distancing (Cruise Industry News, 2021).

This study focused on COVID-19 and how it has affected seafarers and their decision on going back to work under the new normal. This study was conducted because the researchers wanted to determine the impact of COVID-19 on the seafarers' and their employment decisions in the new normal. This study attempted to know what it has been like to work in the cruise line industry under the new normal. This would also be important for other workers who would consider going back to work in the cruise line industry because they would have a basis on what they should consider if ever they would decide to work again in the cruise line industry under the new normal. The researchers hoped that even if the study will not be beneficial to those seafarers who have since returned to work, data collected would still be useful as future references.

Literature Review

According to Yang et al. (2021), the tourism industry has been one of those things that were troubled by the pandemic and hits the scale globally in a critical situation due to the impact that it has brought. Data revealed that the cruise sectors are the ones being affected most by the pandemic in the tourism industry and this has greatly affected the economy of this sector. Because of the damage that the pandemic has brought to the cruise sector, it would be hard for them to recover quickly and is considered to progress at such a slower pace. It is also stated that since the cruise operations were temporarily stopped, then the revenue in this sector had been decreasing initially.

While the operations are temporarily being stopped, the industry will just remain steady and will start operating again when it is safe to do so, and the government granted it as well as considering the numbers of guests. As for the investors, their decisions will most likely be influenced by the current impact of the pandemic in the industry and consider the risks when they tend to invest in it again.

Yang et al. (2021) added that during the Covid-19 pandemic, there were four major travel behavior changes that occur which is the request, the reason, the modes, and the benefit of travel. The travel of normal people who do not work as frontliners such as police officers, and those in medical fields began to minimize. In return to this minimized travel, public transportation becomes the least popular and least used as it is one of the main possible reasons that the virus could be transmitted especially if the number of passengers is not regulated. The decrease in travel demands also leads to a lack of physical engagement and increase in distress.

According to Slišković (2020), the COVID pandemic had an effect in the lives of seafarers who both chose to continue their work and stay in their homes. Those who continued to work are at risk of getting infected with the virus, while being isolated threatens their mental, physical, and social well-being, which affect the performance of seafarers. Those who chose to stay at home are also at risk of financial or economic problems, as well as their own health, due to the pandemic. Slišković's statement is related to our own research as it also tackles the COVID-19 pandemic and how it affected the careers and decision making of the seafarers. This research also made use of the two-factor theory which considers the hygiene and workplace of the seafarers, as well as the safety and hygiene of the work environment itself.

According to Quigley et al. (2021), the cruise line industry was greatly affected by the pandemic because the cruise ship passengers and crew members were at risk of being infected particularly during the start of the pandemic. It is due to the fact that cruise ships accommodates many passengers and crew members onboard. It was also mentioned that while not all the people are vaccinated yet, or at least their passengers, and crew members, then the cruise ship must implement risk management strategies to make sure that the safety of those on board will be guaranteed. Said strategy includes the rapid testing for COVID-19, the use of facemasks, the implementation of social distancing, and strict cleaning protocols. This has affected the crew members too as they are not able to work unless cruise ships get permission for business operation.

Fana et al. (2020) articulated that there are different levels of effect due to the COVID-19 pandemic that has affected the economy in general and the employment sector in particular. The ones greatly affected are those from the low productivity services, while those from the manufacturing activities receive fewer negative effects compared to others as they occur continuously due to their contribution to the community. Based on their scope, Spain and Italy are the two most affected countries in terms of employment than those in other parts of Europe. While in the United Kingdom and southern Europe, the closed sectors had the biggest employment rate, which includes the tourism and accommodation industries. Those countries that have recorded massive income loss due to the pandemic were concerned for the financial stability of their future. One of the major effects of the pandemic is that it could eventually affect how the market works especially if the pandemic continues to affect different sectors of different industries.

According to Da Silva (2021) in his gathered data, the cruise line industry in Florida holds over 149,000 jobs and is responsible for billion wages of employees. It is estimated that over 16,000 jobs were lost in the industry due to the pandemic. The cruise industry is among the most affected as the COVID-19 strikes, which contributes to the joblessness in the state due to the limitation in operations. As an effect, major economic loss was experienced by the industry. Wise planning is needed in order for the industry to restart their operation as there are major adjustments that they must undergo, wherein the US already lifted the ban and restrictions of operations of the cruise lines to set sail.

The workers will then be able to return to their respective work in the industry once the operations restart but there will be many important things and adjustments to consider before they get on board as part of the safety protocols for the benefit of them and the customers. By the time the cruise line industry recovers, the hotel and accommodation, the airline industry, and the tourist spots will also recover as they are somehow interconnected with the customers' interest in their vacations.

Mallapaty (2020), in his published article, maintained that from the cruise ship Diamond Princess, there were about 700 people that were infected by the virus. The said incident led to the further study of the spread of the virus due to its close environment since they are under quarantine. It also shows how the cabin crew are affected, just like how they are quarantined in their respective cabins for more than two weeks to contain the spread of the virus within the ship. Meanwhile, some of the crew members lost their jobs too due to the pandemic, as their cruise ships had temporarily stopped operations because of lack of passengers.

In an article published by DiVincenzo (2020), it explained that the coronavirus had outbreak in China and some cruise ships had impressions that the global pandemic would pose immense danger on people's health. The Princess Cruise Ship had many passengers who were affected by the coronavirus at 712 passengers. In a month's time, the cruise line industry had shut down and had affected the economy considerably as the coronavirus had been affecting so many people. However, the cruise line industry is already back in operation, but passengers need to observe the rules in cruise ships so they can be safe from the coronavirus and that they need to be vaccinated and should always wear mask for protection.

According to Radic et al., (2020), there are some workers from the cruise ship industry that were employed without a contract and did not receive any payment from the time that COVID-19 strikes as cruise ships cease from operating, and at the same time, it was still not known when they would be sent back to their respective countries of origin. Cruise ship workers were also worried about not being able to send financial support to their respective families, aside from not being able to see them, notwithstanding their worries about their health in the middle of the pandemic. Such worries that the cruise ship workers were experiencing affected their mental health and would eventually lead to anxiety, while also having the feeling of fear as they are facing an unseen enemy. Cruise ship workers were also apprehensive that the cruise ships they are connected with would not be able to recover especially if the pandemic continues and operations would not resume soon which in return, would affect their major source of income.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to know how COVID-19 and the ongoing pandemic affects the seafarers and their decisions on going back to work in the new normal. The research attempted to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Gender;
 - 1.3 Cruise line company they work for; and
 - 1.4 Years of service in their respective companies?
2. What is the level of well-being of the seafarers based on the following:
 - 2.1. Mental health
 - 2.2. Emotional health
 - 2.3. Physical health
 - 2.4. Financial health
3. Is there a significant relationship between the seafarers' current mental, emotional physical, and financial states and their decision on going back to work under the new normal?

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant relationship between the current mental, emotional physical, and financial states of the seafarers and their decision on going back to work under the new normal.

Alternative Hypothesis: There is a significant relationship between the mental, emotional physical, and financial states of the seafarers and their decision on going back to work under the new normal.

Significance of the Study

This study wanted to know how the COVID-19 impacted employees and their decision about going back to work under the new normal, hence the following groups of people are seen to benefit from this research:

Tourism Students – This will benefit the students by giving them information about the risks of working under a new normal, as well as ideas to help them decide about their career since cruise line industry is also based on tourism. They can relate to the possible impact of the pandemic to the cruise line industry.

Cruise Line Management Students – This study will benefit them by giving some possible scenarios that they can encounter when they will be working on their chosen field. This will also give them information which will help them decide if they would be willing to start a career in the cruise line industry.

Future Researchers – It will benefit future researchers if they have related studies regarding the factors that affect employment decisions in the cruise line industry or the decision-making of employees towards their career. The same would also be helpful if they are going to conduct and search for information for their studies related to cruise line operations.

Seafarers – This study will help the seafarers to determine whether to return to their work while also evaluating if it is safe to do so. This study will also help the seafarers to broaden their understanding of their situation and plan accordingly based on the factors presented in the study.

Cruise Line Companies – They will be able to know the employment decision rate of the employees and individuals who want to work in the cruise line industry; the companies would be able to know if seafarers are willing to apply or go back to work even if they can possibly experience drastic changes and major health risks in a situation like the COVID-19 pandemic.

Future Seafarers – They will be able to prepare and act accordingly when they experience a situation like the COVID-19 pandemic. They will be able to know how to calculate their decisions related to employment specially in the cruise line industry; as this research provides information about the factors that affect the employment decisions of an individual.

Methodology

Research Design

The study used a quantitative approach, and descriptive research design, which measures the impact of COVID-19 to the decisions of an employee to go back to work under the new normal. A total of 50 respondents took part in the survey and data were collected using simple random sampling.

Sample

There were a total of 18 male and 32 female seafarers, or a total of 50 respondents, who were chosen through simple random sampling. Simple random sampling was chosen so that each respondent has a fair chance of being able to participate in the study through answering the online survey. The participants in this study are the seafarers from the Norwegian Cruise Line, P&O Cruises, Royal Caribbean International, and Holland American Line. They were asked to share their insights about the different factors that affected their decision in going back to work under the new normal.

Instruments

The researcher-made instrument is composed of four statements about the demographic information of the seafarers, four statements for the level of well-being of the seafarers’ mental state, four statements for the level of well-being of their emotional state, four statements for the level of well-being of one’s physical state, and five statements for the level of well-being of the respondents’ financial state. The questionnaire underwent validation as well as reliability test. The reliability testing was done through the JASP reliability test, and the results were automatically generated.

For the mental state and factors, it is revealed in Table 1 that the survey questionnaires are valid and adequate to represent the objectives of the study.

Table 1. Mental state and factors (Frequentist scale reliability statistics)

Estimate	McDonald's ω
Point estimate	0.797
95% CI lower bound	0.669
95% CI upper bound	0.925

Note. Of the observations, pairwise complete cases were used.

For the emotional state and factors, it is revealed in Table 2 that the survey questionnaires are valid and good to represent the objectives of the study.

Table 2. Emotional state and factors (Frequentist scale reliability statistics)

Estimate	McDonald's ω
Point estimate	0.869
95% CI lower bound	0.776
95% CI upper bound	0.961

Note. Of the observations, pairwise complete cases were used.

For the financial state and factors, it is revealed in Table 3 that the survey questionnaires are valid and good to represent the objectives of the study.

Table 3. Financial state and factors (Frequentist scale reliability statistics)

Estimate	McDonald's ω
Point estimate	0.888
95% CI lower bound	0.813
95% CI upper bound	0.962

Note. Of the observations, pairwise complete cases were used.

For the physical state and factors, it is revealed in Table 4 that the survey questionnaires are valid and adequate to represent the objectives of the study.

Table 4. Physical state and factors (Frequentist scale reliability statistics)

Estimate	McDonald's ω
Point estimate	0.706
95% CI lower bound	0.819
95% CI upper bound	0.893

Note. Of the observations, pairwise complete cases were used.

The researchers used a survey questionnaire which was administered to fifty (50) seafarers employed in the Norwegian Cruise Line, P&O Cruises, Royal Caribbean International, Princess Cruises, and Holland American Line.

Data Collection and Gathering

The researchers collected the data through an online survey questionnaire using Google forms and links were sent to the respondents working in cruise line companies like Norwegian Cruise Line, Holland America Line, Royal Caribbean International, Princess Cruises, and P&O Cruises. In order to gather the data, the researchers wrote a letter of request for approval to the course adviser. Once approved, the survey questionnaires were distributed to the respondents online through Messenger. After answering the survey questionnaires, the responses were collected and analyzed.

The researchers determined the impact of COVID-19 to cruise ship employees and their decisions to go back to work under the new normal based on their answers on the given survey questionnaire. Questions for demographic profile are identified using frequency. For question number 2, data were analyzed using the measures of central tendency which is the mean and P values and then the responses for question number 3 were analyzed using Pearson R formula and analysis of variance (ANOVA).

The researchers used frequency distribution for SOP 1, Bayesian-Binomial for SOP 2 per variable, and Pearson R formula for SOP 3. For the pilot testing results, the researchers used McDonald's Reliability Test JASP reliability test; the results of which were generated automatically through the software.

Results

Table 1. Demographic profile of the respondents (n=50)

Variables		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Female	32	64%
	Male	18	36%
Age Range	20-30	18	36%
	31-40	12	24%
	41-50	18	36%
	51-60	2	4%
Cruise Line	Holland America Line	19	38%
	Norwegian Cruise Line	4	8%
	P&O Cruises	14	28%
	Princess Cruises	3	6%
	Royal Caribbean International	10	20%
Years of Working	1-10	29	58%
	11-20	16	32%
	21-30	4	8%
	Less than 1 year	1	2%

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the respondents. In terms of gender, results revealed that there are more females at 32 than males at 18. In terms of age range, it was revealed that there are 18 respondents who are between the ages of 20-30, 12 respondents between the ages of 31-40, 18 respondents between the ages of 41-50, and two respondents between the ages of 51-60. In terms of cruise line, it was indicated that the cruise lines the respondents are currently employed are as follows: 19 under Holland America Line, four are employed under Norwegian Cruise Line, 14 are employed under P&O Cruises, three are employed under Princess Cruises, and 10 are employed under Royal Caribbean International. This table also presented the number of years the respondents have been working in their respective cruise lines. Twenty-nine (29) respondents answered they have worked in the industry for 1-10 years, 16 said they have worked in the industry for 11-20 years, and four said they have worked in the industry for 21-30 years; while one of them was working for less than one year.

Using binomial test, the means and p-values were determined. The responses for each statement that yielded the top two highest means were used to represent the general population knowing that the higher the mean, the greater the weight of the response.

Table 2 shows the different mental state and factors that affect seafarers' decision in going back to work. For Statement 1: *I suffer from mental distraught*, 14 strongly disagreed and 15 had neutral reactions. With both having acceptable p-values, this means that the respondents do not experience mental distraught. For Statement 2: *My mental well-being is better when I am at work*, 14 agreed and 19 had neutral reactions. Comparing p-values, those who have agreed to the statement is tested to be valid at 0.006. Thus, the respondents' mental well-being is better at work. For Statement 3: *I am mentally capable to handle work already*, 21 agreed and 13 strongly agreed. With the agreed sentiment having a p-value of 0.002, this means that the respondents in relation to the population are mentally capable despite the onslaught of the pandemic. For Statement 4: *Overall, my mental health is fit to work*, 18 agreed and 17 strongly agreed. With acceptable p-values, this means that the general population is fit to work based on mental state and factors.

Table 2. Mental State and Factors

Factor	Level	Counts	Total	Proportion	p
I suffer from mental distraught.	1	14	48	0.292	0.006
	2	11	48	0.229	< .001
	3	15	48	0.313	0.013
	4	7	48	0.146	< .001
	5	1	48	0.021	< .001
My mental well-being is better when I am at work.	1	5	48	0.104	< .001
	2	4	48	0.083	< .001
	3	19	48	0.396	0.193
	4	14	48	0.292	0.006
	5	6	48	0.125	< .001
I am mentally capable to handle work already.	1	4	48	0.083	< .001
	2	4	48	0.083	< .001
	3	6	48	0.125	< .001
	4	21	48	0.438	0.471
	5	13	48	0.271	0.002
Overall, my mental health is fit to work.	1	3	48	0.063	< .001
	2	4	48	0.083	< .001
	3	6	48	0.125	< .001
	4	18	48	0.375	0.001
	5	17	48	0.354	0.009

Note: Proportions tested against value: 0.5.

In comparison, the stress level at home does not differ when at work as per the respondents’ reaction on that statement. In fact, the respondents generally do not suffer from mental distraught. Having to know that stress level at home and at work which is not entirely different will attest to the beneficial point that work-from-home (WFH) and face-to-face (F2F) working environments bear the same weight. Using the answers, it is also revealed that the respondents are mentally capable to handle work already, leaving no room for mental judgment that they are not fit to work. Ultimately, the aforementioned mental state and factors prove to be adaptive to the pandemic which allows seafarers to go back to work.

Table 3 shows the different emotional state and factors that affect seafarers’ decision in going back to work. For Statement 1: *I feel happy and contented at work*, 19 agreed and 11 strongly agreed. With both having acceptable p-values, this means that respondents are generally happy and contented on their job flow, career development and working environment. For Statement 2: *I am supported and valued at work which boosts my confidence*, 20 agreed and 13 strongly agreed. Using the p-values, this statement was tested to be valid for all respondents who agreed and strongly agreed at 0.002 and 0.003 respectively. Thus, their work environment boosts their confidence because they are valued as an employee. For Statement 3: *I am influenced by the positive feeling at work*, 19 agreed and 12 strongly agreed. Both answers have 0.002 p-values, which means that the respondents in relation to the population are influenced by positive feelings at work which equates to reduce negative influences. For Statement 4: *Overall, my emotional health is fit to work*, 18 agreed and 18 also strongly agreed. With acceptable p-values, this means that the general population is fit to work based on emotional state and factors.

Table 3. Emotional State and Factors

Factor	Level	Counts	Total	Proportion	p
I feel happy and contented at work.	1	3	48	0.063	< .001
	2	7	48	0.146	< .001
	3	8	48	0.167	< .001
	4	19	48	0.396	0.003
	5	11	48	0.229	< .001
I am supported and valued at work which boosts my confidence.	1	3	47	0.064	< .001
	2	6	47	0.128	< .001
	3	5	47	0.106	< .001
	4	20	47	0.426	0.002
	5	13	47	0.277	0.003
I am influenced by the positive feeling at work.	1	2	46	0.043	< .001
	2	4	46	0.087	< .001
	3	9	46	0.196	< .001
	4	19	46	0.413	0.002
	5	12	46	0.261	0.002
Overall, my emotional health is fit to work.	1	3	48	0.063	< .001
	2	4	48	0.083	< .001
	3	5	48	0.104	< .001
	4	18	48	0.375	0.011
	5	18	48	0.375	0.011

Note: Proportions tested against value: 0.5.

Since the seafarers do not have mood swings at home, and they are most contented at work due the positive feeling brought about by their respective cruise lines as well as the actual support from their co-workers, it is evident on their agreed statements that the respondents are emotionally healthy to be at work. Ultimately, being generally emotionally healthy means that aside from being emotionally prepared to go back to work, there is no hindrance when it comes to emotional state and factors for going back to work.

Table 4 shows the different physical state and factors that affect seafarers decision in going back to work. For Statement 1: *I experience discomforts and back pain*, 15 disagreed and 14 agreed. With the respondents agreed at a p-value of 0.001, this means that they do not experience discomfort and back pain. For Statement 2: *My company has an updated workplace well-being protocol*, 16 agreed and 16 also strongly agreed. Using the p-values, this statement was tested to be valid for both respondents who agreed and strongly agreed at 0.0029 which both equates to the cruise line they are currently working with having an updated workplace as well as implemented protocols in compliance with the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) guidelines. For Statement 3: *The cruise line is clean and safe*, 15 agreed and 18 strongly agreed. Both answers have p-values at 0.013 and 0.011 respectively, which means that the respondents agreed that the cruise line as their workplace is clean and safe. For Statement 4: *Overall, my physical health is fit to work*, 18 agreed and 18 also strongly agreed. With acceptable p-values of 0.013 and 0.001 respectively, this means that the general population is fit to work based on physical state and factors.

Table 4. Physical State and Factors

Factor	Level	Counts	Total	Proportion	p
I experience discomforts and back pain.	1	10	48	0.208	< .001
	2	15	48	0.313	0.013
	3	9	48	0.188	< .001
	4	12	48	0.250	0.101
	5	2	48	0.042	< .001
My company has an updated workplace well-being protocol.	1	3	48	0.063	< .001
	2	6	48	0.125	< .001
	3	7	48	0.146	< .001
	4	16	48	0.333	0.029
	5	16	48	0.333	0.029
The cruise line is clean and safe.	1	2	48	0.042	< .001
	2	5	48	0.104	< .001
	3	8	48	0.167	< .001
	4	15	48	0.313	0.013
	5	18	48	0.375	0.011
Overall, my physical health is fit to work.	1	3	48	0.063	< .001
	2	5	48	0.104	< .001
	3	4	48	0.083	< .001
	4	15	48	0.313	0.013
	5	21	48	0.438	0.001

Note: Proportions tested against value: 0.5.

Since it is established that the respondents were not stagnant, they also attested that they do not feel any physical discomforts which were found true and significant based from the statistical tests. Other than that, they considered their respective cruise safe and clean since they uphold current protocols in compliance with the IATF guidelines. This makes the respondents physically fit to work and the work environment itself is good for them to work again.

Table 8 shows the different financial state and factors that affect seafarers' decisions in going back to work. For Statement 1: *I am more inclined to go to work because I earn money*, 10 disagreed and 15 strongly agreed. With acceptable p-values at 0.009, it means that the general population is really inclined to work because they wanted to earn money. For Statement 2: *I am already below my savings*, 15 disagreed and 14 are neutral. With the respondents answering agreed at a p-value of <0.001 and 0.019 respectively, this means that they still have savings for certain expenses. For Statement 3: *My food and bills are not paid yet*, 13 disagreed and 14 neutral. Using the p-values, this statement was tested to be valid for both respondents who disagreed and felt neutral at 0.002 and 0.009 which equates that they are still on track with their bills.

For Statement 4: *I am financially unstable*, 12 agreed and 11 strongly agreed. Both answers have p-values at <0.001, which means that the respondents agreed that they are on the verge of being financially unstable due to lack of work. For Statement 5: *Overall, my financial health deems me to go to work*, 14 agreed and 14 also strongly agreed. With acceptable p-values at 0.006, this means that the general population is not just fit to work but also deems that they need to work based on financial state and factors.

Table 5. Financial State and Factors

Factor	Level	Counts	Total	Proportion	p
I am more inclined to go to work because I earn money.	1	5	48	0.104	< .001
	2	1	48	0.021	< .001
	3	8	48	0.167	< .001
	4	17	48	0.354	0.009
	5	17	48	0.354	0.009
I am already below my savings.	1	5	47	0.106	< .001
	2	10	47	0.213	< .001
	3	15	47	0.319	0.019
	4	9	47	0.191	< .001
	5	8	47	0.170	< .001
My food and bills are not paid yet.	1	5	48	0.104	< .001
	2	14	48	0.292	0.006
	3	13	48	0.271	0.002
	4	12	48	0.250	< .001
	5	4	48	0.083	< .001
I am financially unstable.	1	8	48	0.146	< .001
	2	10	48	0.229	< .001
	3	12	48	0.250	< .001
	4	11	48	0.229	< .001
	5	7	48	0.146	< .001
Overall, my financial health is fit to work.	1	6	48	0.125	< .001
	2	5	48	0.104	< .001
	3	9	48	0.188	< .001
	4	14	48	0.292	0.006
	5	14	48	0.292	0.006

Note: Proportions tested against value: 0.5.

It is evident that despite paying the food and bills, the respondents considered themselves as financially unstable because they need to go back to work to earn money. Ultimately, the requirement to work because of financial health is very high in order to sustain one’s living.

Using the ANOVA Test of Correlation for all the variables and demographics, it is revealed that there is a positive correlation with the independent variables and dependent variables which in fact affects the respondents’ decisions about going back to work. This means that the cruise line industry offers a clean and safe working environment integrated with a joyous and respectful coworkers that support them. This entails that despite having back logs on finances and physical health, more pull to go back to work is given to them. Thus, with an acceptable p-value of 0.021, the general population is fit to work and will go to work based from emotional, physical, mental and financial state and factors.

Conclusion

There are 32 female and 18 male seafarers that served as respondents of study, the most common age range is 20-30, Holland America Line has the highest amount of seafarer respondents having a total of 19 respondents. It means that there are more female seafarers than male seafarers, and there are more young adults working in a cruise ship. The data also revealed that the most cruise line company that people work for that was surveyed is Holland America Line with the range of 1- 10 as the most number of years the respondents have worked in their respective cruise line companies.

In terms of physical well-being, seafarers are physically fit to work and the work environment itself is good for them to resume working, while in terms of emotional well-being, the seafarers are emotionally prepared to go back to work. There is no hindrance when it comes to emotional state and factors for going back to work, and in terms of mental well-being, it is revealed that the respondents are mentally capable to handle work already, leaving no room for mental judgment that they are not fit to work. Ultimately, the aforementioned mental state and factors prove to be adaptive to the pandemic which allows seafarers to go back to work. In terms of mental well-being, the requirement to work because of financial health is very high in order to sustain the respondents' living conditions.

There is a significant relationship between the respondents' current emotional, physical financial, and mental states and their decision on going back to work. There is a positive correlation between the independent variables and dependent variables which in fact affects the respondents decisions of going back to work.

Seafarers should maximize their break time and enjoy it to lessen their stress levels during work hours because according to an article about the importance of employee breaks. Randolph (2016) articulated that taking breaks can likewise decrease stress. A distressing issue at work can add to negative ways of behaving like peevishness. Skipping lunch a lot can cause stress and weariness. By having some time off away from the issue or eating or having a snack, employees return recharged and ready to handle the following work.

Seafarers should cut off unnecessary expenses and employees should be given the right number of salaries in order for their finances to improve. According to the University of Wyoming (n.d.), cutting unnecessary expenses like dining in a restaurant, television entertainment, switching to a less expensive phone service, unsubscribing to memberships will overall help improve financial stability.

It is also recommended that the readers or future researchers to further study the necessary procedures in availing for a cash assistance program. Since the respondents are seafarers who are classified as OFWs, other types of OFWs who may stumble into this research can also benefit from the same recommendation presented. The Department of Labor and Employment (DOLE) offers cash assistance program to OFWs, which also has guidelines that must be followed for one to avail the program.

The Philippine Overseas Employment Administration (POEA) has issued guidelines that would assure the protection and benefits of Filipino seafarers during unfortunate situations in their deployment or repatriation due to Covid-19 related reasons. A seafarer who signed an employment contract but cannot be deployed from the point of hire due to Covid-19 should be paid basic pay, accommodation, food, and medical benefits at the principal/employer's cost until the seafarer joins the vessel.

References

- Cruise Industry News. (2021, May 4). *'Happy to have a job' crew excited to return to cruise ships*. Pacific Tourism Organisation. <https://southpacificislands.travel/happy-to-have-a-job-crew-excited-to-return-to-cruise-ships/>

- da Silva, A. L. R. (2021). An overview of the impact of COVID-19 on the cruise industry with considerations for Florida. *Transportation Research Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 10, 100391. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2021.100391>
- DiVincenzo, K. (2020, October 2). *What returning cruise ship workers need to keep in mind in a COVID world*. Work-Fit. <https://www.work-fit.com/blog/what-returning-cruise-ship-workers-need-to-keep-in-mind-in-a-covid-world>
- Fana, M., Torrejón Pérez, S., & Fernández-Macías, E. (2020). Employment impact of Covid-19 crisis: from short term effects to long terms prospects. *Journal of Industrial and Business Economics*, 47(3), 391-410. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40812-020-00168-5>
- Gössling, S., Scott, D., & Hall, C. M. (2020). Pandemics, tourism and global change: a rapid assessment of COVID-19. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 29(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669582.2020.1758708>
- Harris, S., Miller, G., Dawsey, J., & Nakashima, E. (2020, March 20). *US intelligence reports from January and February warned about a likely pandemic*. The Washington Post. https://www.washingtonpost.com/national-security/us-intelligence-reports-from-january-and-february-warned-about-a-likely-pandemic/2020/03/20/299d8cda-6ad5-11ea-b5f1-a5a804158597_story.html
- Huang, C., Wang, Y., Li, X., Ren, L., Zhao, J., Hu, Y., Zhang, L., Fan, G., Xu, J., Gu, X., Cheng, Z., Yu, T., Xia, J., Wei, Y., Wu, W., Xie, X., Yin, W., Li, H., Liu, M., ... & Cao, B. (2020). Clinical features of patients infected with 2019 novel coronavirus in Wuhan. *The Lancet*, 395(10223), 497-506. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(20\)30183-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30183-5)
- Mallapaty, S. (2020). What the cruise-ship outbreaks reveal about COVID-19. *Nature*, 580(7801), 18. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-020-00885-w>
- Mercene, R., & Medenilla, S. P. (2020, April 20). *Cruise ship workers out of jobs till end of 2020*. Seafarer Times. <https://www.seafarertimes.com/2018-19/node/4150>
- Quigley, A. L., Nguyen, P. Y., Stone, H., Lim, S., & MacIntyre, C. R. (2021). Cruise ship travel and the spread of COVID-19—Australia as a case study. *International Journal of Travel Medicine and Global Health*, 9(1), 10-18. https://www.ijtmgh.com/article_119534.html
- Radic, A., Arjona-Fuentes, J. M., Ariza-Montes, A., Han, H., & Law, R. (2020). Job demands–job resources (JD-R) model, work engagement, and well-being of cruise ship employees. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 88, 102518. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2020.102518>
- Randolph, S. A. (2016). The importance of employee breaks. *Workplace Health & Safety*, 64(7), 344. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2165079916653416>
- Slišković, A. (2020). Seafarers' well-being in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic: A qualitative study. *Work*, 67(4), 799-809. <https://doi.org/10.3233/WOR-203333>
- University of Wyoming. (n.d.). *Living paycheck to paycheck: cut out unnecessary spending*. https://www.uwyo.edu/finwellness/manageyourfinances/cut_unnecessary_spending.html
- World Health Organization. (2020, January 5). *Pneumonia of unknown cause – China*. <https://www.who.int/emergencies/disease-outbreak-news/item/2020-DON229>
- Yang, Y., Cao, M., Cheng, L., Zhai, K., Zhao, X., & De Vos, J. (2021). Exploring the relationship between the COVID-19 pandemic and changes in travel behaviour: A qualitative study. *Transportation Research Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 11, 100450. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2021.100450>